

ARIES

Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 730871

DELIVERABLE REPORT

ARIES Communication and Outreach Activities – Final report

DELIVERABLE: D2.2

Document identifier:	ARIES-D2.2
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 37 (May 2020)
Report release date:	04/06/2020
Work package:	WP2: Training, Communication and Outreach for Accelerator Science (TCO)
Lead beneficiary:	Oxford
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

The purpose of ARIES Communication and Outreach activities is two-fold: 1) communicate the project developments through Accelerating News and 2) support communication/outreach initiatives across the European accelerator community. A series of activities resulted from trying to fulfil the second point: two workshops and a dedicated section for communication in a newsletter with a wide reach. In turn, these activities allowed us to report on many other activities, meeting the purpose of the task to monitor and report on communication and outreach activities taking place in Europe, many of them featured in this report with greater or lesser detail. Finally, they allow us to propose additional activities for future accelerator communications.

ARIES Consortium, 2020

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see: <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730871. ARIES began in May 2017 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The ARIES Communication and Outreach activities build on the work of previous projects like TIARA and on a short survey conducted in early 2018. With accelerator-based particle physics currently at a crossroads, and the involvement of various stakeholders in decisions about science and technology, communication has become an integral part of every scientific endeavour. The Accelerator Communication and Outreach (ACO) workshops were held to address the need for a platform to share best practices among communication professionals at European accelerator laboratories. While the first workshop focused on a communication strategy, the second looked at the future to define activities the community could develop together.

Other activities from the accelerator community have been invaluable to take accelerator science to its various audiences, especially the less technical, some of them featured in this report.

Finally, participants from the ACO workshops have kindly contributed to this report, identifying the main activities to address the ARIES goals and identify best practices based on the collective experience of the community. A set of activities has been recommended for future communications.

1. Introduction

The ARIES Communication and Outreach activities fall within the scope of WP2 – *Training, Communication and Outreach for Accelerator Science*. The goal of Task 2.2 “Coordination, support and enhancement of communications/outreach activities for accelerators in Europe” is, on one hand, to communicate the project through media such as Accelerating News, a newsletter focused on accelerator science and technology, featuring content from all the major accelerator projects. On the other, it aims to monitor communication/outreach activities across the European accelerator community, sharing best practices via meetings and workshops, as well as identifying actions for improving communications/outreach activities, and facilitating their realisation.

Task 2.2 follows the activities of the EC co-funded project TIARA and builds on the conclusions of the WP5 report “Recommendations for promoting accelerator science and technology in Europe” (2013). More recently, to guide the creation of a network of communication officers at European accelerator laboratories, a survey was conducted between January and March of 2018. The survey comprised six questions and collected answers from 12 institutes/collaborations/networks. The main results of this survey allowed us to identify two key questions:

- 1) How to leverage the existing networks to create opportunities for the accelerator community?
- 2) How to ensure efficient communication among the specific subset of communication officers dedicated to communicating accelerator science, without replicating existing networks?

A series of activities resulted from addressing these questions: two workshops and a dedicated section in a newsletter with a wide reach. In turn, these activities allowed us to report on many other activities, thus meeting the purpose of the task to monitor and report the communication and outreach activities taking place in Europe, many of them featured in this report with greater or lesser detail. Finally, they allow us to propose additional activities for future accelerator communications.

1. Background

Accelerator-based particle physics is currently at a crossroad, with key decisions regarding the next big collider after the LHC expected to be taken within the next few years. The scientific community does not make these decisions alone. Instead, they result from a process involving multiple stakeholders, with both specialised and more general expertise: policy makers, media, industry, and public audiences. Not only is science communication fundamental to overcome the barriers that separate different disciplinary fields and foster new discoveries, as these other key audiences should understand work done in the laboratory, so that science continues to find the support and talent it needs to develop.

For all these reasons, research organisations have become increasingly aware of the advantages of professional communication activities; funding agencies have made these activities a pre-requisite for every project in the EU framework. Communication has become an integral part of almost every scientific endeavour, including accelerator research and development. While this paradigm-shift is a welcome development, there is always room for improvement and learning from the experiences of other colleagues. The Accelerator Communication and Outreach workshops were held to address this need for a platform to share best practices among communication professionals at European accelerator laboratories.

Challenges for the Future

Our activities took place at a time where the future directions for our field are being decided. The *European Strategy for Particle Physics Update*, closely linked to particle accelerators, is expected to be published later this year. Several large-scale new accelerator projects, based on advanced technologies, are aiming for a recommendation to proceed. Many light sources accelerator laboratories are planning major upgrades in the coming decade and several projects are currently in development. Accelerator communication, in this and similar contexts, can be pivotal for the support of such future accelerators. In this – as concluded in the first workshop organised by the Task (Section 2.1) – the accelerator community is united. Therefore, in order to secure funding for the best and most promising new project, the accelerator, particle physics and user communities should have a common communication strategy to address the many concerns of their various stakeholders.

2. Actions

The purpose of Task 2.2 is two-fold: 1) communicate the project developments through a dedicated newsletter and 2) support communication/outreach initiatives across the European accelerator community. In this context, Task 2.2 manages and contributes to Accelerating News. Task 2.2 also organised two *Accelerator Communication and Outreach (ACO) Workshop* in November 2018 and in February 2020. In both, a community of communication officers at accelerator laboratories shared best practices in concrete topics and agreed on specific activities to develop together.

2.1 ACCELERATING NEWS

A quarterly newsletter directed at the broad accelerator community (physicists, engineers, academics, industry), the publication highlights news and results from the biggest accelerator development projects. Currently, Accelerating News [1] has a total of 1'425 subscribers. Since May 2017, 25 ARIES news articles have been published. In 2018, we introduced the Communication and Outreach[7] topic, with eight articles sourced, written and/or edited by Task 2.2 with the community's support. The purpose of this platform is to report on and highlight benchmark activities related to accelerator communication and outreach, help to develop a sense for the importance of communications among the readership, and contribute to building communications skills. In this platform, projects like The Tale of Two Tunnels [2], Project M [3], the Accelerator Game [4], and the Particle Therapy Master Class [5] have been featured, hopefully inspiring other communicators and scientists to try their hand at outreach.

In the most recent website (launched in December 2017), four out of the ten most -read articles in the newsletter are related to ARIES (statistics provided by CERN Web Services). The most read article in the newsletter is ARIES' Bringing particle accelerators on ships [6](with a total of 4'047 views), written in July 2019 on one of the projects funded by the ARIES Proof-of-Concept scheme.

The second ARIES ACO Workshop featured a session dedicated to identify key topics to guide a new editorial plan for Accelerating News, to be considered for the period between July 2020 and July 2021 (See Section 3). Additionally, new tools and services for the Accelerating News email campaign will be considered to align the newsletter with the best practices in the area of digital communication.

A new website will be launched in the summer of 2020 with the support of Task 2.2.

2.2 1ST ARIES ACCELERATOR COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH WORKSHOP

In November 2018, Task 2.2 organized an exclusive, invitation-only the 1st Accelerator Communication and Outreach workshop [7] for the accelerator communication community to share best practices and discuss the future of outreach for accelerators. The workshop aimed to engage the participants in defining how to increase the impact of outreach activities for particle physics, light and neutron sources' accelerators. More specifically, the ARIES ACO Workshop aimed to promote a discussion about resources and best practices, the needs of the accelerator communication community, and provide the basis for common communication activities.

A number of Communication Officers of accelerator infrastructures and Physics centres from all over Europe took part in the workshop and in the discussion about strategic elements for accelerator communication and outreach. Sarah Davies (PCST) was the Keynote Speaker, providing a short talk about Science Communication and Communication Networks. James Gillies (CERN) followed with a precise talk about communication strategy, thus setting the context for the workshop. Each participant had the opportunity to present a communication challenge they had faced in the past and their institution's response, allowing the team to extract challenges and best practices.

The projects mentioned by the community include *Accelerate!* [8] and *Misión ALBA* [9]

Goals, audiences, messages and resources were the focus of the discussion¹. Participants discussed the particulars of a common strategy, the diversity of audiences, the careful choice of channel, and the importance of engaging your neighbours and policy-makers. Participants considered the different goals of various infrastructures and the common messages that concern the whole community.

A news article was featured in both Accelerating News [1] and the PCST network blog [10].

2.2.1 Future Activities

The participants had the opportunity to discuss specific steps that the community could undertake to promote accelerator communication, considering limitations such as resources and different short-term agendas. Participants agreed on:

- A specific category for accelerator communication [11] in Accelerating News
- Explore the possibility of a track in IPAC 2020 for accelerator communication
- A follow-up workshop to be held in February 2020

2.3 2ND ARIES ACCELERATOR COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH WORKSHOP

The 2nd ARIES Accelerator Communication and Outreach Workshop [12] took place on 27-28 February 2020, with the goals of reflecting on our previous conclusions and setting a strategy for future accelerator communication and outreach. It brought together 16 representatives from particle physics, light and neutron sources' accelerators. The workshop aimed at building up on the community's collective experience to support a set of recommendations for future communication activities for the ARIES community.

Pedro Russo, an astrophysicist and science communicator from Leiden University, was the invited keynote speaker. In his talk, Russo presented a series of case studies, highlighting audiences, impact and constraints on the implementation of each project. The workshop had three other defining moments for future ARIES communication activities². A brainstorming session on key topics and issues for future accelerator communication that should guide the new editorial plan for Accelerating News, facilitated by Anais Rassat, the Head of Media Relations at CERN; a brainstorming session for potential communication activities, facilitated by Task 2.2; and a group discussion on activities the community could develop together for the greater impact of accelerator communications.

A news article about the event was featured in Accelerating News [13].

2.3.1 Future Activities

The main takeaways from the workshop are 1) the list of topics of interest for the community and 2) the set of actions the community will undertake together. The list of topics will guide the editorial plan for Accelerating News between July 2020 and July 2021. Broadly defined, these topics are:

- Accelerator upgrades, a thematic series featuring different accelerator facilities

¹ See the event minutes at: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/760778/>

² See the event minutes at: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/877001/>

- The societal and economic impact of accelerators
- The community's contribution to the UN sustainable development goals (SDG)
- A series of interviews and opinion pieces from different experts

Additionally, Accelerating News will provide a platform for the community to share educational material, with the instructions to build a 'cardboard accelerator' (a contribution from the project participants) being the first addition to this repository to be hosted in the new website of Accelerating News, to be launched in the summer of 2020, with the support of Task 2.2.

2.4 OTHER ACTIVITIES FROM THE ACO COMMUNITY

In addition to the initiatives reported during both ACO workshops and through the dedicated category in Accelerating News, other activities from the accelerator community have been invaluable to take accelerator science to various audiences. In this section, we mention a few of the events that took innovative approaches to put accelerator development and impact in the spotlight.

2.4.1 Particle Colliders – Accelerating Innovation

The *Particle Colliders: Accelerating Innovation Symposium* was co-hosted by the University of Liverpool and CERN, with partners from the Future Circular Collider and EuroCirCol projects. On 22 March 2019, almost 1,000 researchers, university staff and students, as well as high school students, attended the event at the ACC Liverpool. The keynote talks were live-streamed to more than 10 countries, and an industry exhibition and workshop served as an innovation platform and career fair. ARIES featured in a dedicated stand, where previous issues of *Accelerating News* were presented. Audio-narration of all talks made the Symposium the first fully inclusive accelerator science event for visually impaired audiences. More than a dozen bespoke outreach activities communicated the physics and engineering of accelerators in an engaging way, including the Surfatron, the virtual reality app acceleratAR [14], Tactile Collider [15], and CERN's interactive LHC Tunnel.

The event featured in Accelerating News [16].

2.4.2 Accelerators for Science and Society

The *Symposium Accelerators for Science and Society* took place at the ACC Liverpool on 28 June 2019, organised by the University of Liverpool and supported by the MSCA networks [Accelerators Validating Antimatter](#) [17] and [Optimisation of Medical Accelerators](#) [18] as well as the [Liverpool Centre for Doctoral Training in Data Intensive Science](#). [19] It aimed to provide an insight into the economic, scientific and societal benefits of particle accelerators and inspire students with the possibilities in this rapidly evolving field. Talks were live-streamed to partner organisations across Europe. One highlight was presentation given by bestselling author, illustrator and animation creator Curtis Jobling, best known as designer of the worldwide hit television show 'Bob the Builder'. He shone a light on how innovation needs both STEM and creative subject areas. His fun and engaging talk '[Full STEAM ahead](#)' [20] was a highlight for the audience – young and old alike.

The event featured in Accelerating News [21].

2.4.3 CERN Open Days 2019

Under the banner “Explore the future with us” of the CERN Open Days 2019, the CERN Knowledge Transfer Group organised an exhibition at IdeaSquare in September, where visitors could explore the medical, aerospace and cultural heritage applications of CERN’s technology. Around 75’000 people visited the laboratory during the event, and around 2’000 people visited IdeaSquare. Visitors had the opportunity to see the real-life compact particle accelerator used for art analysis, the PIXE-RFQ. One of the projects funded by the ARIES Proof-of-Concept was also featured at the event.

2.4.4 The Physics of Star Wars

On 20 November 2019, UK-based physicists from the Cockcroft Institute and the University of Liverpool used Star Wars to engage local schoolchildren with accelerator physics. The proton torpedo used by Luke Skywalker to destroy the death star was linked to hadron therapy, and the hovering speeder bikes seen on the forest moon of Endor to superconductivity and future colliders. Lightsabres provoked discussions on the laser knives used for precision surgery and materials treatment, and students sliced virtual cubes using virtual-reality headsets and controllers. Experiments with liquid nitrogen heightened awareness of Han Solo’s precarious situation when frozen in carbonite – and of the LHC’s ultra-low-temperature vacuum pipes. Finally, force telekinesis led to conversations about the Paul traps used to capture antihydrogen ions in experiments carried out at the AD facility at CERN. The event reached more than 1 Million people through digital media and global press.

3. Future Accelerator Communication and Outreach

Communications can play a role in each of the ARIES goals:

1. To develop and demonstrate novel concepts and further improve existing accelerator technology.
2. To provide researchers and industry with access to top-class accelerator research and test infrastructures.
3. To enlarge and integrate the European accelerator community.
4. To develop a joint strategy for securing sustainable accelerator S&T.
5. To support innovative technologies with market potential by advancing concepts and designs for medical, industrial and environmental applications of accelerators for the benefits of European society as a whole.

While objective (1) is a largely technical objective, there is an interest in communicating its results to many stakeholder groups, ranging from potential funding agencies to members of the public. Such communication is likely to be handled by individual institutions, although there may also be interest in communicating such news within the accelerator communications community.

Objective (2) could be helped by developing a communications channel that reaches those in targeted industries and research establishments. Accelerator conferences and an electronic newsletter such as Accelerating News are obvious candidates. An analysis of Accelerating News readership might help to identify areas where the newsletter could be further promoted.

Objective (3) requires communication internal to the community. This could also be served through conferences and a newsletter, whether the same as that targeted at potential users or not is a subject for discussion. A network for communicators in the field could also be very useful here in enabling the communicators to develop, collaborate and reach their audiences effectively. Objective (4) will

require targeted communication once the strategy exists, in order to make sure it is known by future stakeholders, and objective (5) is a source of stories that could be used to build support for the field.

3.1 BEST PRACTICES

There is an ideal order for every communication activity. The first step is defining the goal of a certain activity. What does one want to achieve? This goal will be the basis for everything that follows. Then one should find the right audience for this goal. These two factors are key and, once they are clear, the tools and the key messages that will reach this audience to achieve this goal should be easily defined. Finally, evaluation is key to demonstrate one's impact and inform future activities.

The communications team should have close links to or be part of the project's management. They should be among those who define strategies, rather than simply carry out the work. Especially since R&D projects for accelerators do not exist for the sake of the accelerator technology alone: they facilitate fundamental science, applications outside physics research, and find an important partner in Industry for the benefit of all parties. As a consequence, communication for accelerator R&D is never just about the accelerator. Many projects will need a cultural or geo-political context (e.g. SESAME), a historical context or an organisational context (e.g. future accelerators such as CLIC and FCC).

Once accelerators evolve from ideas and test stands to proper projects, another element features heavily in accelerator communication: the surrounding community. People living in the neighbourhood of the facility will want to understand associated potential hazards, noise, and construction work. In addition to talking about the amazing benefits accelerator technology can bring to society, the communication team must open a channel to deal with the very down-to-earth questions and concerns of their neighbours. Just as for decision-makers, one needs one's neighbours on side.

3.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

From the two previous sections, a small number of tangible actions that the accelerator community might wish to consider follow:

- The production of a **targeted newsletter** or newsletters for key audience segments.
- The further development of a communications culture by **working with the major accelerator conferences** to include communications in the agenda. The community could associate public-facing events to the conferences and provide supporting marketing material.
- In addition to marketing material, the community could also provide **educational material**.
- While an additional formal network beyond *interactions.org* or *lightsources.org* would appear to be unnecessary and potentially costly to run, the establishment of a PCST-style mailing list, to which any interested party could subscribe, could foster collaboration between those with an interest in accelerator communications.

4. Future Plans for the ACO Community

In the last year of the ARIES project, Task 2.2 will continue supporting the work of Accelerating News, including setting up the new website, sourcing and editing articles related to ARIES and Accelerator Communication and Outreach, and by setting up the new editorial plan for the newsletter.

In addition, Task 2.2 will continue to document communication/outreach activities both through the newsletter and through a repository of outreach materials to be hosted at the new Accelerating News website, and collaborate to communicate the many ARIES advancements through partner channels.

5. Annex I: List of Projects and Activities - References

- [1] [Accelerating News](http://acceleratingnews.eu/) (<http://acceleratingnews.eu/>)
 - [2] [The Tale of Two Tunnels](#)
 - [3] [Project M](#)
 - [4] [Accelerator Game](#)
 - [5] [Particle Therapy Master Class](#)
 - [6] ARIES' [Bringing particle accelerators on ships](#)
- [7] [1st ARIES Accelerator Communication and Outreach Workshop](#)
 - [8] [Accelerate!](#)
 - [9] [Misión ALBA](#)
 - [10] [PCST network blog](#)
 - [11] [ACO Accelerator communication](#)
- [12] [2nd ARIES Accelerator Communication and Outreach Workshop](#)
 - [13] Accelerating News: [Building on the community's collective experience on accelerator communication](#)
- **Particle Collider – Accelerating Innovation**
 - Surfatron
 - [14] [acceleratAR](#)
 - [15] [Tactile Collider](#)
 - CERN's interactive Large Hadron Collider Tunnel
 - [16] Accelerating News : [How fundamental science is changing our world](#)
 - [17] [Accelerators validating Antimatter](#)
 - [18] [Optimisation of Medical Accelerators](#)
 - [19] [Liverpool Centre for Doctoral Training in Data Intensive Science](#)
- **Accelerators for Science and Society**
 - [20] Talk: [Full STEAM ahead](#)
 - [21] [Accelerator News: Accelerators for Science and Society](#)

- **CERN Open Days 2019**
 - Technologies that change our lives, IdeaSquare
- **The Physics of Star Wars**